

SITE CHARACTERIZATION REPORT

IV.ISPIC: Ispica (RG)

Giuseppe Orefice¹, Alfio Marco Borzi¹, Antonino D'Alessandro², Francesco Panzera¹

¹Dipartimento di Scienze Biologiche, Geologiche ed Ambientali, Università degli Studi di Catania, Catania

²Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Sezione di Palermo, Palermo

Solid Earth Geophysics Lab

Università degli Studi di Catania

Corso Italia 57, 95129 Catania (CT)

Corresponding authors:

giuseppe.orefice@phd.unict.it

Contents

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Geological settings.....	3
3. Active seismic measurements and processing	4
3.1 Equipment	4
3.2 Geometry of the acquisition array.....	5
3.3 Acquisition.....	6
3.4 Processing	6
3.4.1 Rayleigh wave data f-k processing	6
4. Passive seismic measurements.....	7
4.1 Acquisition and equipment.....	7
4.2 Single station processing.....	8
5. Inversion of surface wave data.....	9
5.1 Inversion target	9
5.2 Parameterization of the model space	10
5.3 Inversion results	10
6. Interpretation of the velocity profiles.....	10
6.1 Velocity profiles	10
7. Discussion and conclusions	11
References.....	11

3. Active seismic measurements and processing

The active seismic line was deployed close to ISPIC station (about 15 m far), along a N-S direction (Fig. 2). For the sake of a comprehensive subsurface characterization, Multichannel Analysis of Surface Waves (MASW; Park et al., 1999) was conducted.

Fig. 2 Satellite view of the study area and acquisition layout. Green triangle: ISPIC seismic station; red triangles: MASW array; red stars shot points; blue triangles: single station measurement point.

3.1 Equipment

To conduct the site characterization, we used a set of 25 vertical-component geophones (4.5 Hz corner frequency). The geophone set was connected to a SoilSpy Rosina datalogger. An 8-kg sledgehammer hitting a flat metal plate was used as seismic source at two shot locations (red stars in Fig. 2) positioned outside the geophone line. The synchronization between the traces recorded by the geophones and the seismic source was ensured by the first geophone-trigger.

3.2 Geometry of the acquisition array

The vertical-component geophones were deployed at regular intervals of 2 m (Fig. 2), resulting in a total length of 48 m. The geophones were installed using metal spikes inserted into the ground to ensure proper soil coupling (Fig.3). The shot points were placed at the two ends of the deployment 10 m distant from the last geophone (red stars in Fig. 2). At these shooting positions the sledgehammer was vertically blown on a flat metal plate for Rayleigh wave generation (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Geophone array in place. The picture was taken near the nord-east end of the line (viewpoint N to S).

3.3 Acquisition

In Fig. 4 we show a representative seismic gather obtained from a hammer shot. The acquisition parameters adopted for MASW was the following: sampling frequency 256 Hz, record length 3 s, pre-trigger delay -0.6 s. At the source points, 6 hammer shots were blown and the traces generated were saved in separated .sg2 file (without automatic stack).

Fig. 4 Examples of acquired seismic sections from vertical component wave shot.

3.4 Processing

3.4.1 Rayleigh wave data f-k processing

Rayleigh wave dispersion characteristics were extracted from the vertical component seismograms from MASW survey. The achieved seismic records were processed by using $f-k$ (frequency – wavenumber) transform (Kvaerna and Ringdahl, 1986), to obtain a conversion of the recorded sets of traces from time vs. distance to frequency–wavenumber domain and then Rayleigh waves

dispersion curves. To improve the Signal-to-Noise ratio (S/N), the Rayleigh wave dispersion curve panels from single shot records with the same source position were summed produced staked spectral images (O’Neill, 2003; Neducza, 2007). The energy maxima of the Rayleigh wave dispersion curves were picked on these stacked panels; spectral amplitude peaks from individual shot records were identified and used to define the uncertainty intervals in the estimation of phase velocities (Socco et al., 2009; Boiero and Socco, 2010). Fig. 5 shows the dispersion panels obtained from the considered seismic records together with the stacked dispersion curve derived from the forward and reverse acquisitions, as well as the corresponding picked energy maxima. The dominant feature in both spectra considering the shot in the S and N position is a branch extending continuously in the frequency band 12.0-40.0 Hz. This feature is interpreted as superimposition of Rayleigh wave modes.

Fig. 5 Phase velocity versus frequency stacked spectra obtained considering the recordings from the two shot points at the N and S ends of the deployments and the total stacked curves.

4. Passive seismic measurements

4.1 Acquisition and equipment

In addition to the active seismic survey, four single-station noise recording measurements were performed on the same acquisition day (Blue triangle in Fig. 2). The sensors (SmartSolo IGUDB3C-5 seismometer) were partially buried in the ground to improve coupling with the soil (Fig. 6). The sampling frequency was 200 Hz, and the recordings spanned a 40-minute time interval.

Fig. 6 Single-station IGUDB3C-5 ambient vibration recording.

4.2 Single station processing

The ambient vibration recordings were processed with the aim of estimating the H/V ratio of recorded noise, thus identifying the fundamental frequency of resonance of the site (Nakamura, 1989) using classical H/V methods as implemented in Geopsy software (www.geopsy.org; Wathelet et al., 2020). The results of the different measurements points show a generally consistent spectral ratio curve, indicating limited lateral variability in the investigated area (Fig. 7).

The HVSR curves exhibit a relatively flat ratio over most of the investigated frequency range, consistent with stiff subsurface conditions. A weak broad increase in amplitude is observed at low frequency between approximately 1.0 and 2.0 Hz, possibly associated to heterogeneity of the medium. The HVSR at the measurement point SS_03176 shows a slightly high amplitude value in between 1.0-2.0 Hz, but this can be attributed to increasing wind during the measurement. As can also be observed from the increase of standard deviation.

Fig. 7 H/V ratio versus frequency obtained from the processing of noise recording data.

5. Inversion of surface wave data

The Rayleigh wave dispersion curve obtained from the processing of active seismic data were inverted for the 1D S-wave velocity profile of the investigated site. For the inversion the Dinver code implemented in Geopsy (Wathelet et al., 2020) was used. The code provides a set of Vs models compatible with the observed dispersion curve. This inversion tool uses a directed-search method, called “neighbourhood algorithm” (Sambridge, 1999).

5.1 Inversion target

The target we selected for the inversion (Fig. 8) consists of:

- The Rayleigh wave dispersion curve, as obtained from the processing of active data with the f-k processing. The forward and reverse shot dispersion curves showed good agreement; therefore, a stacked dispersion curve combining both directions was adopted for the analysis to improve the frequency range coverage.
- Two modes were identified and used in the inversion.

5.2 Parameterization of the model space

For the parameterization of the subsurface model, the soil column was represented as a stack of four homogeneous layers overlying a half-space. Within each layer, V_s values were allowed to vary within broad boundaries (50–3500 m/s).

5.3 Inversion results

We performed the inversions using the Dinver routine (www.geopsy.org). The inversion run produced 200000 total models in order to assure a good exploration and exploitation of the parameter space. The result of the inversion is shown in Fig 8. The 4-layer parametrization yields slightly lower misfit values 0.02; however, the velocity profiles are generally consistent.

Fig. 8 Dispersion curves for the Rayleigh waves and S-wave velocity profiles. The red line indicates the best-fitting model.

6. Interpretation of the velocity profiles

6.1 Velocity profiles

The inverted V_s profile (Fig. 8) shows an increase in shear-wave velocity with depth ranging from 600–800 m/s in the shallowest layers to 1400–1700 m/s below 10–15 m depth. The shallowest layers are characterized by V_s values of approximately 600–800 m/s, indicating already stiff near-surface conditions. At depths of about 10–12 m, a clear velocity increase is observed, with V_s reaching values of approximately 1400–1800 m/s and locally higher values at greater depth.

The derived V_{s30} value of 949 ± 10 m/s indicates very stiff ground conditions and the site can be classified as soil class A according to both Eurocode 8 (EC8) and NTC 2018. The overall velocity structure is consistent with the relatively flat HVSR response at the site.

7. Discussion and conclusions

The HVSR analysis at the ISPIC station shows a generally flat spectral ratio response, consistent with stiff ground conditions. A weak resonance is observed at frequencies 1.0-2.0 Hz, suggesting the presence of vertical layer heterogeneities.

The inversion of the active seismic measurements provided a Vs profile characterized by a progressive increase in shear-wave velocity with depth. Near-surface layers exhibit Vs values of approximately 600–800 m/s, while velocities increase up to ~1400–1800 m/s below ~10–11 m depth, indicating the presence of stiff geological formations.

The derived V_{S30} value of 949 m/s classifies as soil class A according to both Eurocode 8 (EC8) and NTC 2018, confirming stiff subsurface conditions.

References

- Boiero, D., & Socco, L. V. (2010). Retrieving lateral variations from surface wave dispersion curves. *Geophysical prospecting*, 58(6), 977-996. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2478.2010.00877.x>
- Fäh, D., Kind, F., & Giardini, D. (2001). A theoretical investigation of average H/V ratios. *Geophysical Journal International*, 145(2), 535-549. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.0956-540x.2001.01406.x>
- Kvaerna, T., & Ringdahl, F. (1986). Stability of various fk estimation techniques. *NORSAR Semiannual technical summary*, 1, 1-86.
- Lentini, F., & Carbone, S. (2014). Carta Geologica della Sicilia—Scala 1: 250.000. *Servizio Geologico d'Italia—ISPRA: Firenze, Italy*, 7-414.
- Nakamura, Y. (1989). A method for dynamic characteristics estimation of subsurface using microtremor on the ground surface. *Railway Technical Research Institute, Quarterly Reports*, 30(1).
- Neduczka, B. (2007). Stacking of surface waves. *Geophysics*, 72(2), V51-V58. <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.2431635>
- O'neil, A. (2003). Full-waveform reflectivity for modeling, inversion and appraisal of seismic surface wave dispersion in shallow site investigations. *PhD, The University of Western Australia and School of Earth and Geographical Sciences*.
- Park, C. B., Miller, R. D., & Xia, J. (1999). Multichannel analysis of surface waves. *Geophysics*, 64(3), 800-808. <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.1444590>
- Sambridge, M., 1999. Geophysical inversion with a neighbourhood algorithm—I. Searching aparameter space, *Geophysical Journal International*, 138(2), 479–494. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-246X.1999.00876.x>

- Socco, L. V., Boiero, D., Foti, S., & Wisén, R. (2009). Laterally constrained inversion of ground roll from seismic reflection records. *Geophysics*, 74(6), G35-G45. <https://doi.org/10.1190/1.3223636>
- Wathelet, M., Chatelain, J.L., Cornou, C., Di Giulio, G., Guillier, B., Ohrnberger, M., Savvaidis, A., 2020. Geopsy: A User-Friendly Open-Source Tool Set for Ambient Vibration Processing. *Seismological Research Letters*, 91(3), 1878–1889, <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220190360>